

Deliverables

D.8.7 – *Zero Hidden Hunger EU* project website

Author's name: Debora Serra, Nina McGrath

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Zero Hidden Hunger EU project website

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Contributors:

Name	organisation
Debora Serra	EUFC
Nina McGrath	EUFC

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable D8.7 refers to work undertaken as part of Task 8.1 (Rolling Dissemination, Communication & Engagement (DCEP) and Communications Tools, M1-48). It describes the development of an initial project webpage (M1) and plans for the development and launch of the branded project website (M4) and key performance indicators for measuring impact. The Zero_HiddenHunger_EU project website will serve as the main gateway and essential source of information for all project audiences. It will provide comprehensive details about the project's objectives, research, partners, news, events, results and outputs (see section 3).

2. Development of the initial project webpage

During the first month of the project, it was decided to create a temporary landing page for the project on EUFIC's existing website, to ensure that the project has an online presence from the start, while the technical and content development of the full project website was taking place.

This page was published on 29 January 2024 at the following link:

<https://www.eufic.org/en/european-projects/project/zero-hidden-hunger-eu-tackling-mi-cronutrient-malnutrition-and-hidden-hunger-to-improve-health-in-the-eu>

The landing page contains a description of the project, partner list, and contact information for the Coordinator and the EUFIC team. It also acknowledges the funding received from the European Commission.

HOME | EUROPEAN PROJECTS
 ZERO HIDDEN HUNGER EU: TACKLING MICRONUTRIENT MALNUTRITION AND HIDDEN HUNGER TO IMPROVE HEALTH IN THE EU

Zero Hidden Hunger EU: Tackling micronutrient malnutrition and hidden hunger to improve health in the EU

1 January 2024 – 31 January 2027

Overview

Contacts

Micronutrient deficiency is a form of malnutrition that occurs due to low intake and/or poor absorption of minerals and vitamins and can negatively affect human health and development. Children, adolescents, women of reproductive age (including during pregnancy) and older adults, as well as immigrant and ethnic minority groups and those affected by social inequality or poverty, are particularly at risk of micronutrient deficiencies. This represents around 70% of European citizens.

While addressing this public health problem is a priority, better data are needed on the prevalence and causes of micronutrient deficiencies across different regions and population sub-groups in the EU. These data would allow us to predict and identify those most at risk, and centre them in discussions about how to implement measures to support individuals in meeting dietary requirements for micronutrients of the highest public health concern.

In response to this pressing issue, the Zero Hidden Hunger EU project aims to generate comprehensive data on the prevalence of micronutrient deficiencies across the EU population and identify root causes.

Zero Hidden Hunger EU will:

- 1 provide estimates of the true prevalence of micronutrient deficiencies, based on priority biomarker and micronutrient intake data in European populations, and their associated health costs, focusing on high-risk population subgroups
- 2 produce and disseminate the best possible evidence to develop context-specific, tailored food-focused solutions to ensure an adequate supply of vitamins and minerals from diets from sustainable sources

Starting with existing high-quality data and biobanks from diverse and representative population sub-groups across Europe, and supplementing these resources with targeted studies in under-represented groups, Zero Hidden Hunger EU aims to deliver credible evidence that will empower policymakers and food system actors to devise effective food-focused strategies, eradicating micronutrient deficiencies from Europe.

The Zero Hidden Hunger EU consortium brings together expertise from 19 organisations, including public and private sector healthcare professionals, top-tier universities and research institutes, as well as social entities such as NGOs and regional governments, to develop effective knowledge and evidence-based solutions to micronutrient deficiencies.

Partners:

- Project coordinator: University College Cork - National University of Ireland, Cork (UCC) - Ireland
- UCC Academy Designated Activity Company (UCCAC) - Ireland
- Wageningen University (WU) - Netherlands
- Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU) - Denmark
- Syddansk Universitet (SDU) - Denmark
- European Food Information Resource (EUROFIR) - Belgium
- Harokopio University (HUA) - Greece
- International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) - France
- Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) - Finland
- Max Rubner Institute (MRI) - Germany
- Consorcio Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red M.P. (CIBER) - Spain
- Institute for Medical Research and Occupational Health (IMR) - Serbia
- European Food Information Council (EUFIC) - Belgium
- European Public Health Alliance (EPHA) - Belgium
- CrowdHelix Limited (CHX) - Ireland

Associated partners:

- Swiss Nutrition and Health Foundation (SNHF) - Switzerland
- REM Analytics SA - Switzerland
- University of Surrey - UK
- Quadram Institute Bioscience (QIB) - UK

Categories

- Healthy living
- What's in food?
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Figure 1: Screenshots of the initial project webpage

3. Development and launch of the project website

The domain for the Zero_HiddenHunger_EU final project website was purchased on 16 January 2024. The website will be hosted at www.zerohiddenhunger.eu.

The navigation bar at the top of the website will lead visitors to the following pages:

Homepage: Represents the entry point to the website and contains the project’s mission statement and a brief explanation on what the project is about. It will show a preview of the latest project news and contain a newsletter registration form.

About: On this page, visitors can learn more in-depth about the project and its ambitions, and the partners that are involved. A scrollable banner with partner logos will lead visitors directly to the “Partners” page.

Zero_HiddenHunger_EU (subpage): Aimed at providing a more comprehensive overview of Zero_HiddenHunger_EU's scientific activities, including why the project is needed.

Background information on micronutrients (subpage): Contains clear and accessible info on what micronutrients are, why they're important, and where to find them.

Partners. Contains a graphical index with all partner logos that, when clicked, leads to a dedicated page about the partner. Here the visitor can learn more about the partner institution and its role in the project.

News & Events: Shows all the project news, upcoming events related to the project topic and press articles in which the project has been mentioned.

Resources. Any type of public resources that Zero_HiddenHunger_EU will create will be uploaded here (e.g., infographics, videos, publications, newsletter, roll-up banners, etc.) and made available for download. The resources section contains a filter option for the type of resource that should be displayed.

Glossary. Contains an alphabetically sorted list with project-related terms and their definitions. The aim of the glossary is to make content-specific words easily understandable to the reader, including those who may not be familiar with the topic.

Contact. Displays a contact form that the website visitors can use to reach out to EUFIC and the Zero_HiddenHunger_EU coordination team. The form requires users to insert their name, surname, e-mail address and message, as well as to accept the privacy and cookie policy.

The website will be linked to the project's various channels and (social) media platforms, including the SciFoodHealth Twitter/X and LinkedIn accounts MicroNutrient Helix, and the Sustainable Food Systems Network.

The project website has been launched on 30 April 2024 (Month 4) and is accessible at the domain www.zerohiddenhunger.eu.

In addition, project partners will post project content on their organisations' websites and share project news in their newsletters and social media, linking to the Zero_HiddenHunger_EU website to increase traffic.

4. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators (KPIs) have been defined for the Zero_Hidden_Hunger_EU website.

Number of page views = 30,000 by project end (M48)

Number of blogposts/news items = at least 4 per year

Number of newsletters = at least 1 per year

The number of page views, unique visitors and time spent on page will be monitored on a quarterly basis, starting from M6 until the end of the project.